

Human-Algorithm Relationships: Moving Beyond the Interaction as a Site of Empirical Research

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ABSTRACT

As the algorithmic retrofitting of everyday interactions steadily advances, so does the need to understand how humans and algorithms influence each other over time. For this purpose, the *interaction* has become the primary site of empirical research. Yet, the relational, spatial and temporal boundaries that the interaction brings to bear are poorly defined, largely outdated and often restrictive. This results in novel findings aggregating to already worn-out narratives where the interaction is the only way algorithms participate and transform everyday life. In contrast, the concept of relationship, which entails relational, emotional, temporal, and spatial dynamics more attuned to how humans and algorithms increasingly influence each other, has received little attention. Borrowing Robert Hinde's framework of "patterned interactions=relationship," this provocation challenges the limits of the interaction and argues that the relational boundaries of a relationship open up new opportunities for empirically researching how humans and algorithms influence each other over time.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Human-centered computing** → Human computer interaction (HCI); HCI theory, concepts and models; Human computer interaction (HCI); Empirical studies in HCI.

KEYWORDS

Ethnography of algorithms, Critical Algorithm Studies

ACM Reference Format:

Ignacio Garnham. 2024. Human-Algorithm Relationships: Moving Beyond the Interaction as a Site of Empirical Research. In *Designing Interactive Systems Conference (DIS Companion '24)*, July 01–05, 2024, IT University of Copenhagen, Denmark. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 5 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3656156.3663715>

1 INTRODUCTION

Algorithm-driven technologies (often mislabeled as AI technologies) are taking increasingly influential roles across scales of social structure from the familiar to the institutional and political. The implications of algorithms becoming relevant actors in social practices have sparked a need to better understand how humans and algorithms influence each other through empirical examinations of human-algorithm interactions [1, 2]. As a result, the interaction

between humans and algorithms has become a site of ethnographic research. Yet, the relational, spatial, and temporal characteristics that define how the interaction as a research site should be approached are ill-defined.

The challenges inherent to conceptualizing the interactions between humans and algorithm-driven technologies go back to the early days of HCI [4]. Paradoxically, these include both the need for diverse definitions [5] as well as the lack of a common definition [6]. For the former, attention has been raised concerning the lack of guidelines for researchers to recognize and productively engage with the varied forms of interaction that emerge alongside advances in algorithm-driven technologies [7]. During the last decade, the concept of an interaction in HCI has become so fuzzy that some have argued for the need to fully dispose of the term interaction [8, 9]. In the words of Hornbæk and Oulasvirta, "the term interaction is field-defining, yet surprisingly confused" [7, p. 5040].

Yet, amongst these disagreements, and amid an exponential and relentless increase in the frequency and duration of human-algorithm interactions, as well as in the rate and places of exposure to algorithm-driven technologies as part of everyday life, little attention has been placed on discussing the extent to which particular forms of interaction that become sustained in time can evolve into relationships, and what are the implications of this relational transition. The concept of relationship matters for HCI research as it entails relational, spatial, and temporal dynamics that are more attuned to how humans and algorithm-driven technologies increasingly influence each other. Yet, even across papers that purposefully rely on the concept of relationship to highlight informal aspects of the interaction that are otherwise difficult to bring to the fore, such as the use of emotions derived from repeated interactions with algorithms as evaluative feelings, the construction of imaginaries of algorithms as meaning-making practices, and the use of memories and expectations as patterning devices, the concept of relationship remains largely untheorized [for a notable exception, see 17].

Consequently, across HCI literature, the term interaction is frequently used interchangeably with that of relationship, which suggests that researchers focusing on the complexities that emerge from the interactions of humans and algorithm-driven technologies are largely unaware that concepts like interaction or relationship create "descriptions of real-world phenomena related to human use of computing" [16, p. 4958] which in turn shape how these practices are designed and studied. Before moving forward, it is essential to highlight that the concept of "relation," often used to describe the study of human-x technologies in HCI research, merely states that two things are somehow related but says nothing about the type of relation taking place (e.g., professional, emotional, social),

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DIS Companion '24, July 01–05, 2024, IT University of Copenhagen, Denmark

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ACM ISBN 979-8-4007-0632-5/24/07

<https://doi.org/10.1145/3656156.3663715>

where and how often it takes place, what purpose it serves, and what power dynamics it entails.

To argue why human-algorithm relationships should be approached as distinct sites of empirical research, I borrow the concept of “patterned interactions” proposed by Hinde [10] as part of his interaction-relationship-structure framework. While Hinde’s framework builds on behavioral sciences and anthropology to discuss the social structure of non-human primates rather than human-like algorithms, it has been thoroughly demonstrated that humans often approach and form relationships with technologies—such as computers and algorithms—in similar ways as they do with people [11, 12]. Yet, despite growing evidence about social relationships between humans and algorithm-driven technologies, there is scant theoretical and methodological support for approaching those relationships as distinct from the interaction [13]. As a result, novel findings emerging from the ethnographic turn in HCI are aggregated to already worn-out narratives where the interaction is the only way in which algorithms participate and transform everyday life. This provocation aims to help advance a use and understanding of the term relationship for HCI research that moves beyond a mere analogy to be instead used as a cognitive tool for reframing how humans and algorithms influence each other over time.

The provocation begins with an overview of the “interaction” as a relational concept for humans and algorithm-driven technologies based on recent examinations of the challenge, namely by Hornbæk and Oulasvirta [7] and Reeves and Beck [3]. It continues with an introduction to patterned interactions and the particulars of a relationship according to Hinde’s framework and concludes with a discussion of opportunities and challenges for researching human-algorithm relationships.

2 THE TERM INTERACTION IN HCI

As previously mentioned, there are diverse propositions for what the term and concept of interaction should entail. In significant part, this is due to the growing variety of ways in which humans and algorithms interact with each other, which give rise to sub-fields of study such as interactive systems, interaction design, multimodal interaction, ubiquitous interaction, data interaction and many more. Yet, the diversity of ways in which the interaction can take place does not mean that there are no definitions of the term interaction. Alas, attempts to define the relational, spatial and temporal conditions of the interaction are often akin to dictionary definitions [14], where the emphasis is placed on 1) that interactions are of a reciprocal nature, 2) that a transaction of “something” (e.g. information, goods, services) needs to take place, and 3) that such transaction will have an influence on one or both of the parts involved in the interaction.

Regardless of how the interaction is defined, each attempt to categorize a specific type of interaction as a sub-field of research is meant to bring to the fore distinct aspects that are relevant for conceptualizing, designing, and using computing technologies. Hornbæk and Oulasvirta use HCI literature to group diverse aspects and forms of interacting into seven concepts. Namely, interaction as dialogue, transmission, tool use, optimal behavior, embodiment, experience, and control. These concepts set different boundaries to how and when humans and algorithms interact, mainly, as the

authors observe, by constricting A) what is understood as the driver of the interaction, for example the user, artefact, message, interface or site, B) which aspects of the interaction are understood to influence each other, which can leave for example, a tool or a practice out of the scope, and C) the time-scales of the interaction, which vary from the on-the-spot to the over-time. As Reeves and Beck [3, p. 20] put it, the concept of interaction “is about research practices as much as it is about the words HCI researchers use when they generate talk and texts.” In other words, characterizations of an interaction that are too wide or too narrow can affect how researchers design research questions, analyze data, and interpret the impact of algorithms as social actors.

In addition to the three types of boundaries observed by Hornbæk and Oulasvirta, I contend that interaction concepts create a fourth boundary resulting from their treatment and attention to formal and informal elements, of which the former has received disproportionate recognition. I borrow the concepts of *formal* (containing a mathematical structure) and *informal* (without a mathematical structure) elements as they are used in art and design for relating elements in a composition to instead relate the parts in an interaction. For the purpose of studying human-algorithm interactions, I refer to formal elements as those needed for a transaction to take place, such as lines of codes, hardware, interfaces, sensors, and touch screens. Informal elements, on the other hand, are those aspects of the interaction that are intangible, emergent, and often unaccounted for, such as feelings, emotions, perceptions and expectations. Formal and informal elements, as described in the following section, are central for analyzing the content, quality, and time scales that set the conditions for how algorithms and humans relate to one another.

3 FROM INTERACTIONS TO RELATIONSHIP

It is well-documented that the interactions between humans and algorithms are becoming more diverse and frequent across social structures. For Hinde [10], interactions are the motors of social structures, but he leaves the definition of what constitutes an interaction to those defining the problem space and context of study. Essentially, rather than focusing on the details of individual interactions, Hinde’s framework aims to shift attention to how and why some interactions become patterned. To be clear, this is not to say that the elements that define an interaction, which Hinde refers to as content (i.e., what humans and algorithms are doing together) and quality (how they do it), are irrelevant. On the contrary, Hinde emphasizes that an interaction needs to be well-defined and understood before attempting to elucidate how such interaction becomes patterned.

Before moving forward, it is relevant to highlight that there is an essential distinction between the repetition and the patterning of interactions, as only the latter will evolve into a relationship. Repetitions are scaffolded by formal elements that lack emotional investment, such as using a voice assistant to program alarms and timers. On the other hand, using voice assistants as conversational agents for socialising brings to the fore informal elements (emotions, feelings, desires) that, over time, become patterned and influence the nature, frequency, duration and outcome of the interaction [15]. Consequently, in order to differentiate repetition from

pattern, Hinde places a great deal of attention on the time span and continuity through which informal elements emerge and become exchanged and negotiated by the interacting parts as it is through the patterning of informal elements that the meaning-making practices that allow the different parts in a relation to “begin to know each other as individuals” [10, p. 6]. Once the content, quality and temporality of the interaction have been described, Hinde shifts attention to the notion of relationship.

In keeping with the time span of interactions at the centre of the analysis, Hinde defines a relationship as “a series of interactions in time between two individuals known to each other” [10, p. 6]. The emphasis that the two parts interacting know each other is meant to reinforce two things. Firstly, as previously described, that informal elements are being negotiated as part of the interaction. Secondly, that a relationship between two individuals is always influenced by the content and quality of their previous interactions. Therefore, no fixed number of interactions can be said to be “enough” to give way to a relationship. Instead, Hinde’s approach aims to shift the focus of attention to identifying which informal elements are responsible for sustaining a series of interactions over time, how these elements influence how the related parts perceive the quality of the interaction, and what power dynamics result from the exchange and negotiation of informal elements. Consequently, informal elements must also be studied in relation to expectations about future interactions, as these will also determine how the interacting parts get to “know each other” over time.

While the ways in which humans and algorithms get to know each other are constantly shifting between text, touch, vision and voice, current interaction paradigms are still heavily dependent on formal elements that constrain the temporality and space of possibilities; you can only speak so far or loud (if your accent or language affords you the possibility, that is), touch requires even closer proximity, vision is dependent of external factors that are often out of control, and text is inherently normative. Consequently, users of the same algorithm-driven technology tend to interact, at least formally, in very similar ways with their algorithmic counterparts. This, in turn, results in particular types of interactions frequently being associated together to create broader relational frames. For example, a human-voice assistant relationship could be a larger frame for patterned interactions such as learning, socializing, and assisting. Yet, Hinde warns that similar patterns of interactions grouped under a broader relational frame can, and often will, result in widely different relationships for the interacting parts as these learn and adjust their behavior to each other. To illustrate this challenge, Hinde provides the example of a monkey mother-infant relationship, which involves several subsets of patterned interactions such as nursing, maternal grooming, protection, and play. These interactions are laden with informal elements that can quickly change the nature of an interaction and the type of relationship that is built on them while still allowing for the hyphenation of mother-infant to describe the relationship, which can hide from the analysis deeper structural elements that are central to understanding the unfolding of relationships over time.

The stability of a relationship over time, therefore, should be considered in dynamic terms. As patterns of interactions are adjusted over time, so will the content and quality of the informal

elements being exchanged and negotiated, which in turn will continually modify not only when but also where the interacting parts influence each other. The “where” is relevant for Hinde because relationships as meaning-making practices are not bound to the limits of the interaction (e.g. text, touch, voice, and vision) and are often influenced by diverse aspects of everyday life that may or may not relate to the interaction under examination. Hence, tracing the patterning of interactions and the emergence of relationships is, on the one hand, as much, if not more, about fleshing out meaning-making practices that relate to the past and future as it is about the real-time experience of the interaction. On the other hand, it is about identifying meaning-making practices that occur not only before, during and after the interaction but also “outside” the interaction. In the case of the human counterpart of the interaction, these can involve aspects related to mood, behavior and reasoning that become apparent as the individual interacts with other things, technologies, people and sites that trigger reflection about the individual’s interactions with the algorithm [19]. As Hinde puts it [10, p. 9], a relationship “implies a time dimension, and its description must be based on data gathered over a period of time.” The same logic must be applied to the algorithmic counterpart, as its objectives and reward functions are also subject to be modified to account for emerging changes in use and frequency amongst its user’s base. This examination will prove increasingly more challenging as algorithmic systems continue to become black-boxed [20], which can potentially perpetuate a one-sided understanding of the conditions that shape human-algorithm relationships.

As algorithm-driven technologies continue to become a part of daily life, so does the need for empirically researching how algorithms become part of larger social practices. While HCI research currently lacks a shared understanding of what the term relationship affords for the study of human-algorithm interactions, researchers who rely on the term often highlight its significance through aspects that are central to Hinde’s “patterned interactions=relationship” framework. For example, concerning the temporal dimensions of interactions and how the ways in which users experience a specific interaction over time can condition the exchange and negotiation of informal elements [13, 18], that over time, the exchange of certain informal elements can evolve into patterns that can influence the behavior of the interacting parts [21], and that a relationship between humans and algorithms occurs when the interacting parts begin to determine each other’s behavior over a sustained period of time [7]. Understanding and operationalizing the concept of relationship not as an analogy but as a cognitive tool for reframing how humans and algorithms influence each other over time can provide a valuable resource for critically examining the relational shifts that will determine how algorithms transform social life.

4 DISCUSSION

The concepts of interaction and relationship are equally relevant for understanding how social structures and networks are formed, maintained, and changed over time as algorithms become part of them. Yet, there is a pressing need for these concepts to be studied as complementary yet different phenomena and to position

the concept of relationship as a distinct area of study that warrants specific theoretical and methodological approaches. This gap presents an opportunity for the growing number of researchers who are interested in the informal aspects of the interaction but lack the theoretical and methodological frameworks to critically examine the emergence of human-algorithm relationships. In this provocation, I put forward the notion of patterned interactions as a theoretical framework to trace and scrutinize the emergence of human-algorithm relationships and their role in shaping cultural practices and hegemonic narratives of algorithmic life.

Hinde's framework, although initially designed for the study of non-human primates, has contemporary relevance as algorithms are increasingly developed to mimic how (for now, a small subset of) human behaves culturally and socially. By adapting Hinde's theory to HCI challenges, this provocation aims to provide a stepping stone for bringing empirical studies of algorithms closer to the non-algorithmically mediated practices of daily life where formal elements cease to condition the interactions between humans and algorithms and informal elements become the medium through which human-algorithm relationships are forged. Still, additional research is needed to pave the road for the term relationships to transcend the realm of analogies and become instilled as an inescapable condition in the coevolutionary dynamics of algorithmic and social systems. In the following subsections, I highlight three areas needing attention to further describe relationships through patterns of interactions.

4.1 Informal Elements

As our interactions with algorithms increase exponentially, there is a pressing need to understand the content (what humans and algorithms are doing together) and quality (how they do it) of human-algorithm interactions through empirical methods that look beyond the formal elements that relate humans and technologies through code and focus instead on the informal elements of the interaction, and the types of research methods that informal elements afford and require. Notably, a focus on informal elements can be supported by design anthropological (DA) methods, which provide the critical and analytical tools and concepts to approach emergent cultural phenomena [22] by involving research participants in co-creating knowledge [23, 24] through reflection and observation of how emergent technologies shape and become part of everyday life [25, 26]. Still, while DA offers a productive toolset, the increasingly black-boxed nature of algorithm-driven technologies will require engineers and computer scientists to commit to ethnographically assessing the impact of the technologies they develop. On the one hand, this need presents a challenge as ethnographic theory and methods are mostly lacking in the curricula of technical disciplines. On the other hand, this challenge presents an opportunity to encourage interdisciplinary collaborations; we need "technical" people in the field as much as technical processes need social scientists. This kind of interdisciplinary empirical research of algorithms is being spearheaded by the emergent field of critical algorithms studies [27]. Yet, there is still a substantial need for ethnographic researchers to look beyond the formal boundaries of the interaction.

4.2 Context of study

One of the defining characteristics of relationships as meaning-making practices is that they are not bound to the formal elements that define the relational boundaries of human-algorithm interactions. Yet, current empirical research on algorithms is primarily conducted in relation to the code, artefacts, interfaces, and sensors that allow humans and algorithms to interact. This approach is problematic as it often fails to account for the impact that algorithms have in everyday life practices that are not algorithmically mediated and how these practices shape our interactions with algorithms in return. The focus on the interaction as the primary site for empirically studying algorithms is largely due to an outdated understanding in HCI research that algorithms are inseparable from hardware and software and, therefore, must be examined in relation to them. Yet, in recent years, a growing number of researchers are advocating for an understanding of algorithms that is determined "by social engagements rather than by technological or material constraints" [28, p. 3]. This approach has been embraced by critical algorithm researchers since the early days of the field, leading to the term algorithm being scrutinized to a degree that some researchers warn has created more challenges than opportunities. As Striphas [29, p. 2] puts it, the term algorithm has become "heuristically imprecise, infused with its own predilections, and taken up as a catchphrase." Still, for better or worse, "terminological anxiety", as Seaver [1, p. 2] reflects, "[has become] one of critical algorithm studies' defining features," and taking stock of the malleability of the term can be a productive resource for scrutinizing how people speak about their relationships with algorithms alongside other social and cultural phenomena shaping social life.

4.3 Social life of algorithms

Unlike the social relationships of primates, algorithms that have been programmed to behave as social actors are in constant search for the next interaction. More so, most algorithmic models are rewarded for extending those interactions in time and frequency. Consequently, before operationalizing Hinde's framework, it is crucial that the ethnographic researcher understands the social parameters of the algorithms being empirically examined. Failing to acquire such understanding can lead to a researcher patterning a particular type of interaction based on temporal dynamics that are the result of programming rather than of an evolving relationship. Yet, as algorithmic systems grow in opacity [30, 31], this knowledge will be increasingly harder to obtain. This challenge, as with the ones described in the previous subsections, will require interdisciplinary collaboration between social and technical researchers with the objective, as Hinde puts it [10, p. 7], of "describing a particular relationship over a particular time span" by paying close attention to "what the participants in the relationship do together, how, and how often." In keeping in line with design anthropology approaches, Kopytoff's [32] proposition of *object biographies*, which is concerned with the need to examine the entire life cycle of technologies—from production to exchange and consumption—as a method for tracing the diverse situations and practices that imbue meaning and agency to things that inherently have none. Appadurai [33] advances this approach through the concept of *the social*

life of things, which focuses on how the relationships between objects and people are constructed over time as objects—from rocks to trinkets to complex technologies—become influential in the unfolding of social and cultural practices. As the purpose and potential of algorithms continue to become appropriated and reinterpreted in social discourse and practice, they allow themselves to be approached as having a social life [34]. Scrutinizing the social life of algorithms can provide productive theoretical and methodological guidelines for tracing patterns of interactions across broader spatial and temporal dimensions while keeping the focus on the social and cultural practices that unfold alongside the emergence of human-algorithm relationships.

5 CONCLUSION

This provocation introduces the theoretical framework of “patterned interactions=relationship” to identify emergent relationships between humans and algorithms. I contend that the focus on relationships can shift attention to the informal elements in human-algorithm interactions that are often unaccounted for in HCI literature, despite emotions, feelings and desires increasingly being responsible for how humans and algorithms relate. Still, the term relationship, just as much as the term interaction, needs to be better defined when researchers speak about such dynamics becoming a part of social structures. This is not to say that HCI research needs a single definition for these and other relational terms, but that when in use, researchers should be able to provide a detailed account of why the human-algorithm relation under study is being approached as an interaction, relationship, configuration, collaboration, and so on. This increase in granularity requires an ethnographic study of algorithms that engages with the social dimensions of algorithms not only when examining the content and quality of interactions but also when tracing informal elements outside the spatial and temporal boundaries of the interaction. Ultimately, the relational framing of human-algorithm relationships aims to contribute to a better understanding of the diverse and evolving ways in which algorithms become part of and determine the unfolding of social life.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work is part of the DCODE project. The project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955990.

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